

**Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe
Phase 3**

**Report on the first summer schools
Deliverable D5.1**

EuroHPC
Joint Undertaking

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ESiWACE3 Deliverable D5.1

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1. Abstract /publishable summary

The first ESiWACE3 summer school was organised together with the WarmWorld project at the Hotelli Korpilampi in Espoo , Finland between August 27th and September 2nd 2024. The event aimed to bring together young researchers and software engineers interested in the current technological developments in the field of high-performance computing for climate and weather applications. The 17 participants attended lectures and practical sessions, guiding them through the fundamentals of performing weather and climate simulations on modern HPC systems and managing and analysing Earth system model data. The training material was prepared and presented by seven topical experts from CSC, DKRZ and the University of Helsinki.

2. Conclusion & Results

The summer school was organised in accordance to the in the ESiWACE3 grant agreement. New training material was developed for the summer school and the pedagogical review improved the quality of the presentations. This training material is published alongside this deliverable. The summer school was generally received very positively with some critique and suggestions that were at times contradictory to feedback from other participants. This included suggestions to, for example, include more sessions on certain topics (AI/ML, workflows, 3D visualization), but feedback also included a comment that the program was comprehensive and risked covering too much rather than too little. There are two related Key Performance indicators: K13 the number of participants, and K15 the percentage of specific groups represented at ESiWACE events. The summer school had (target Key Performance indicator):

- 17 participants (K13: target was 30 participants);
- all of the participants were early career scientist (K15: roughly 50%);
- 8 of the participants were women (K15: more than 20%).

3. Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to achieving all the macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1 of the Grant Agreement:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable?
A1: Transfer and establish knowledge and technology for efficient and scalable simulations of weather and climate across the Earth system modelling community in Europe	yes
A2: Close common technology gaps in the knowledge and toolbox for high-resolution Earth system modelling via joint developments across the European community.	yes
A3: Serve as a sustainable community hub for training, communication, and dissemination for high-performance computing for weather and climate modelling in Europe.	yes

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Specific goals in the work plan	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1: Increase efficiency of weather and climate simulations on state-of-the-art supercomputers.	no
O2: Design tools to close technology gaps for high performance computing.	no
O3: Develop tools to tackle the data challenge of high-resolution weather and climate modelling.	no
O4: Support the wider community of weather and climate modelling in the use of state-of-the-art supercomputers via targeted services.	no
O5: Support the wider community of weather and climate modelling in the use of state-of-the-art supercomputers via training and capacity building.	yes
O6: Build a well-connected and inclusive community for high-resolution Earth system modelling across Earth system science and HPC and establish connections and knowledge transfer between existing European initiatives.	yes

4. Detailed report on the deliverable

Planning for the first summer school started in November 2023, after the first ESiWACE3 hackathon that was held at CSC. This included the confirmation of co-operation with the WarmWorld project as well as generating an initial topic list, and agreeing on tentative dates for the event. Afterwards CSC asked for offers from different venues located at the Helsinki greater metropolitan area. Two of these offers went through a more thorough scrutiny and were both deemed acceptable.

Fig 1. Photo of summer school participants.

The length of the summer school was set to 7 days (originally 7–10 days) based on budget calculations made with 30 participants and 8 mentors and a participation fee set to 500 € + vat. with the rest of the costs covered by project funding. The dates were selected in agreement with the other mentors. One mentor had to cancel their participation later on.

The advertisement for the summer school started in early May 2024 with a final registration deadline in mid-June and confirmation of acceptance at the end of June. We accepted 28 attendants to the summer school – there was a confirmation and payment period of a couple of weeks for the participants (some also required Visas) during which 10 of the accepted did not confirm their participation (one actual cancellation).

We developed new training material for the first summer school and will give more detailed information on this and feedback in the next section. The training material will be published on the ESiWACE website (<https://www.esiwace.eu/>).

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4.1. Training material, usefulness and feedback

The training material preparation started in early 2024 by agreeing on initial summer school structure, responsible person(s) for different sections, timetable for material preparation and pedagogical review. These plans were revised during the material preparation and a final version was realised as a themed block structure (also shown in Fig 2.):

- B1 (L1–L3): Modelling of weather/climate in the age of HPC and AI
- B2 (ICON, L4–L6): ESM data management, evaluation and visualisation
- B3 (L7–L9): MPI, OpenMP, hybrid and GPU programming
- B4 (L10): Novel concepts

	Tue 27.8.	Wed 28.8.	Thu 29.8.	Fri 30.8.	Sat 31.8.	Sun 1.9.	Mon 2.9.
6-9		Breakfast	Breakfast	Breakfast	Breakfast	Breakfast	Breakfast
9-12	Arrival and introductions	L2: Introduction to HPC	Hands on With ICON	L5: ESM result visualisation	L7: MPI	L8: OpenMP and hybrid programming	L10: Novel concepts
12-13	Lunch	Lunch	Lunch	Lunch	Lunch	Lunch	Lunch
13-15.30	L1: Classical modelling	L3: Modern modelling	L4: ESM data management	L6: ESM result evaluation	free	L9: GPU programming	Departure
15.30-16	Coffee	Coffee	Coffee	Coffee	Coffee	Coffee	
16-17	Student presentations	L3 continued	L4 continued	L6 continued	free	L9 continued	
17-19		Voluntary exercises	Voluntary exercises	Voluntary exercises	smoke sauna 17-23	Voluntary exercises	
19-21	Dinner	Dinner	Dinner	Dinner	Dinner	Dinner	

Fig 2. ESiWACE3 summer school 2024 timetable and structure.

Pedagogical review on material slides was done by the University of Helsinki and achieved by the end of July – this allowed final modifications to be made to the slides. Some material (such as L10 slides and videos) were not ready by the time of the review, so no pedagogical review was completed for those.

We asked feedback from the participants on various aspects of the summer school and report here the average scores (scores were given on a range of 0–5 ranging from bad to excellent):

- Information about the event 3.81
- Registration and payment 4.69
- Course content matched the course description 3.94
- Prerequisites were well defined 3.31

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- | | |
|---|------|
| • The lectures were clearly presented and comprehensible | 3.69 |
| • Teaching aids used (e.g. slides) were well prepared | 3.88 |
| • The hands-on exercises and demonstrations were a valuable contribution to the event | 4.13 |
| • I learned skills that are relevant to my work/research | 4.00 |
| • Overall, how would you rate this event (from 1–10) | 7.94 |

Feedback was also requested with open questions, and we have condensed the answers below (full report is annexed to this deliverable).

What did you like best about the summer school?

Participants appreciated the breadth and relevance of topics, particularly in parallel and GPU programming (MPI, OpenMP, OpenACC), HPC systems, and modelling. Hands-on sessions and practical exercises were highlighted as valuable learning opportunities. The venue and surroundings were highly praised, offering a mix of learning and relaxation in nature. Extracurricular activities were enjoyable and contributed to a positive experience. Opportunities to meet and connect with peers and experts were highly valued. Participants found the lecturers approachable, supportive, and willing to clarify doubts. Many highlighted the overall friendly, helpful, and engaging atmosphere throughout the summer school.

Was there something missing from the summer school?

Participants suggested additional sessions on AI/ML, workflows with HPC, modelling, and basics for less experienced attendees. More practical, hands-on guidance and short 3D visualization were also requested. Clearer communication about the target audience and program prerequisites, such as prior knowledge of Fortran, would help participants prepare better.

The tight schedule, including weekend sessions, was a challenge for some. Suggestions included clearer venue information, transportation assistance, and a day dedicated to group problem-solving to enhance creativity and engagement. Participants also desired better-prepared materials and improved communication among instructors to ensure clarity.

While some felt the program covered too much rather than missing content, others wished for certificates and a larger participant pool. Overall, better organization and targeted improvements in content delivery were identified as areas for enhancement.

What would you like to see changed?

Participants suggested allocating more time for hands-on exercises, small projects, and guided activities to enhance engagement. Several requested clearer preparations and a more structured, pedagogical approach to the lectures and exercises, with templates and advanced options for faster learners. Some felt that content like visualization and ESM analysis could be reduced, while

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basics or introductions to parallel/GPU programming tools in Python should be added. A slower pace and more detailed explanations for beginners were also recommended.

Improved clarity in scheduling, instructions, and audience targeting was highlighted. Examples included unclear exercise guidelines, vague schedules, and lack of communication about social events like the sauna.

Suggestions included grouping students for exercises, balancing content with participant backgrounds, and offering free afternoons for local exploration. Starting on a Monday and ending on a Friday was preferred over weekend sessions. Enhanced planning and communication overall were emphasized.

Was the duration of summer school good or would you like to see it changed?

Many participants felt the summer school should be extended to 10–14 days to allow deeper learning, more practice sessions, and better accommodation of diverse experience levels. Additional time could enhance meaningful connections among attendees and allow for introductions to foundational topics like Fortran, AI/ML, and climate models. A longer duration might also facilitate a free day for excursions, such as visiting Helsinki.

Some participants found the existing length of seven days adequate, but a few suggested minor changes, such as starting on Monday afternoon or ending later in the week.

One respondent preferred a shorter duration of five days, while another suggested balancing fewer topics with a deeper focus if the current duration is maintained.

Please give any other general comments or feedback about this event or any other issues arising from it.

Participants praised the event as a valuable and enjoyable learning experience, highlighting the approachable instructors, well-timed breaks, and the friendly atmosphere. Many expressed gratitude for gaining new knowledge, skills, and materials to build upon independently. The scenic location added to the event's appeal.

Participants suggested integrating sightseeing trips, as the remote location limited opportunities for exploring the area. Other recommendations included avoiding lectures on Sundays to improve scheduling and incorporating minor adjustments to enhance the overall experience.

General Impressions: As a first iteration, the event was well-received, with attendees recognizing its potential for further refinement. Despite some logistical and structural challenges noted in earlier questions, participants generally found the summer school highly rewarding and expressed appreciation for the opportunity. Small changes could elevate it to an even better event in the future.

5. References

There are no references for this deliverable.

6. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered

No changes were made to the plan. For future events, we will shift the start of advertisement earlier to allow more time for registration before summer and Visa application processes etc. We will also ensure that the given feedback will be reflected on both the organisation of the events as well as the training material.

7. How this deliverable contributes to the EuroHPC strategy

The summer school contributes to the EuroHPC strategy by training young scientists in methods, tools and theoretical knowledge needed to effectively use HPC environments in their research, and by providing up-to-date training material for independent usage to anyone interested.

8. Sustainability

The summer school was organised together with the WarmWorld project and this co-operation will continue. The next summer school in 2025 is planned to be held from late July to early August near Hamburg, Germany. The summer schools are an essential tool in both training young scientists, and supporting in building their network.

9. Community engagement, dissemination, and exploitation

9.1 Target audience

As indicated in the Grant Agreement the audience for this deliverable is:

X	The general public (PU).
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This report is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

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This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience:

The training material will be made publicly available at the ESiWACE3 website.

9.2 Record of dissemination/engagement activities linked to this deliverable

Type of dissemination and communication activities	Details	Date and location of the event	Type of audience	Zenodo Link	Estimated number of persons reached

None.

9.3 Publications in preparation OR submitted

In preparation OR submitted?	Title	All authors	Title of the periodical or the series	Is/Will open access be provided to this publication?

None.

9.4 Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable

None.

ESiWACE3&WarmWorld Summer School 2024 Feedback Report

01 1) Where did you hear about the event?

1. LinkedIn

2. The employee

3. from supervisor

4. Institute

5. School's advertisement

6. From Esiwace website

7. Email advertisement from supervisor

8. Searching on Google for summer schools with HPC and climate.

9. A Post-Doc at TUM forwarded the announcement on the LUMI users mailing list to the mailing list of my master's program

10. Met-Jobs

11. Mailing list

12. metjobs and through friends

13. Warm-World mattermost channel.

14. FMI channels

15. former advisor sent it to me

16. met-jobs

Respondents in total: 16

02 Other, please specify

Respondents in total: 0

03 2) Please rate your level of expertise in the topic prior the course

1:	0 / 16
0 %	
2:	2 / 16
13 %	
3:	2 / 16
13 %	
4:	2 / 16
13 %	
5:	3 / 16
19 %	
6:	4 / 16
25 %	
7:	3 / 16
19 %	
8:	0 / 16
0 %	
9:	0 / 16
0 %	
10:	0 / 16
0 %	

Respondents in total: 16

avg. 4.88

2) Please rate your level of expertise in the topic prior the course

04 3) Please rate the following in terms of quality

Information about the event	avg. 3.81
Registration and payment	avg. 4.69

Respondents in total 16

05 4) Please rate the following statements

Course content matched the course description	avg. 3.94
Prerequisites were well defined	avg. 3.31
The lectures were clearly presented and comprehensible	avg. 3.69
Teaching aids used (e.g. slides) were well prepared	avg. 3.88
The hands-on exercises and demonstrations were a valuable contribution to the event (only if applicable)	avg. 4.13
I learned skills that are relevant to my work/research	avg. 4

Respondents in total 16

06 5) The pace of teaching was

1: 0 %	0 / 16
2: 19 %	3 / 16
3: 44 %	7 / 16
4: 25 %	4 / 16
5: 13 %	2 / 16

Respondents in total: 16

avg. 3.31

07 6) What did you like best about the summer school?

1. The breadth of the topics covered and the relevance with the current advancements in the field.
2. I really liked the place mixed with technical content. So you had opportunity to challenge your knowledge during the day and enjoy being in nature quickly on evening.
3. The Hotel was really nice, I enjoyed being there with the other students a lot! The content of the MPI and OpenMP and GPU programming was really interesting and the most usefully and interesting for me.
4. It was very nice to get some experience in attending a summer school and meeting new people ad get some good connections. In addition the place where we stayed was awesome. Some practical exercises were also very helpfull and I had the feeling that I learned during these sessions.
5. The people :)
6. What I did the best about summer school is how helpful everyone was. Including the lecturers was ready to spend time to clear your doubt and help you in every step.
7. The selection of topics, hand on sessions, parallel/gpu programming
8. The location, the people, the extra-curriculum activities were amazing. The lectures on OpenMP, MPI and OpenACC were very relevant and well-structured. The exercises in Fortran were well-planned and at a good level.
9. OpenAcc, travelling to Finland and meeting students from outside my computer science and engineering bubble
10. Location of the summer school, and lecturers are really friendly and helpful.
11. Learning more from HPC and ESM experts since I work closely with HPC systems and modelling. Networking with people.
12. Got better ideas about the HPCs and AI/ML modelling. Also people were super approachable for the hands on training.
13. I liked the venue. I found the contents of summer school covered a good variation of the topics.
14. The OpenMP, MIP, GPU & ICON parts
15. Obviously, the place was incredible, as well as the extracurricular stuff. The lecturers were nice, really open for questions and keen to help with anything. Good atmosphere.
16. - the venue was really nice. - the atmosphere in general between students and the teaching board was also enjoyable

Respondents in total: 16

08 7) Was there something missing from the summer school?

1. May be a couple of sessions on AI/ML specifically.

2. No

3. I would have like to learn more about workflows with coding and running things on HPC systems. To be able to improve my skills on performing and organising my self well.

4. more practical hands-on sessions with a bit more guidance - I wasn't super experienced, so it was a bit difficult to work on the tasks without having an idea what to do

5. More modelling contents so I can know how the programming paradigm is implemented in the existing models

6. May be more basics.

7. a bit more about the ML and novel concepts hands on (if possible) would be nice, short 3D visualization maybe

8. I wish there

9. More clear information about who the target audience is

10. numbers of participant can be increase, add the certificate

11. I'd like maybe for a day of doing a challenge in groups, of like an afternoon or morning, to enhance problem-solving and creativity, in something new. In one of the topics, and towards the end of the course. Exercises were a little short or too expositive. But I understand that the schedule was tight.

12. Tight schedule (saturday and sunday too!). It would be more easy if some more information is provided about the venue and possible means of transportation (arrangement of bus is really helpful))

13. I think it would be more helpful if in some lectures the materials were a bit more prepared in advance. Sometimes I had the filling that the tutors did not teach in a very understandable manner.

14. Some clearer instructions at times, maybe more communication between the instructors.

15. I don't really understand the question, but for a summer school, the subjects covered are, in my view, more likely to be too much than to miss something.

16. I would have liked to have more specific information about the program. For example, I would have liked to know that some of the exercises are in fortran in order to prepare myself in advance to focus on the tasks of the exercises rather than actually learning how to run a fortran code for example.

Respondents in total: 16

09 8) What would you like to see changed?

1. Make it longer with more time for hands-on exercises and may be small projects.

2. Not so much on visualization and basic xarray stuff, most of us seemed to be quite familiar with this.

3. I would like to see a change in the exercises, it should be more guided or there should be a better preparation for the students to have an idea during the exercises....maybe the background of the students should be a bit more focused, so that there is a common knowledge among them and the prerequisites are more similar

4. More preparation on the exercises (the ones from MPI and openmp were good enough)

5. I think you can add more basics or less content so to get more time to expertise.

6. Depending on the audience it might be great to also shortly present/introduce the parallel/gpu programming tools in python. The ESM analysis part could have been a bit shorter for me as I already had a lot of knowledge on that field

7. I hope that there might be a bit more energy put into the course being more pedagogical. The lectures were not always very well planned (teachers not knowing how long the lectures would take; had planned to little for the time given; did not give clear instructions on how much time we had for exercises, or when we should reconvene after a break) and with no actual exercises for the first few days - more just "yeah, just play around with it. Just try whatever". I hope that the next iteration could have clear exercises (and maybe more of them, so if you are done quickly, you can continue to more advanced stuff). It lacked a bit of structure, and somewhat the organizers taking responsibility and communicating more clearly: When do we meet? Why has the bus not arrived yet? What is a sauna and what is appropriate dresscode?

8. Make more clear who the target audience is on the website and in announcements to mailing groups

9. It can be go more slow, and detailed for understanding the person who heard some big terms first time.

10. Personally, I didn't like that I didn't have an afternoon to visit Helsinki.

11. Little more hands on training and bit easy ones.

12. - I would change the way of doing exercises. I would suggest that they designed in was that can be done in groups of three maybe and via discussion. _ I would make the exercises a bit more practical in proportion of backgrounds of participants. - I would start on Monday and end on Friday. _ If I were the torture, I would make a bit more effort to talk louder and slower.

13. As above, the instructions and general schedule were at times too vague. For example, it felt as if staying for the 5-7 voluntary exercises was discouraged. The quality/usefulness in the exercises and learning material varied a lot. Personally, I found the OpenMP & MPI & GPU exercise format (templates to modify with readymade solutions) most useful. Also, the smoke sauna event would have required much more information beforehand: as there are attendees from all over the world, and sauna is such an intimate event, it would have been crucial to inform well in advance how the turns are taken between men/women and what the dresscode for the sauna is.

14. Maybe a clearer structure, more clear exercises and structure, like in the last two days. Also, I prefer approaching a topic in some kind of bottom-to-top manner, say "This is the package we are going to use. Its purpose is like this, its workflow like this and the outcome can be this and this. Using it works mostly in this steps, you have these options." Or so? I mostly had no idea what was actually going on in the code snippets and changed them by trial and error, while not really having an idea of the structures, types and possibilities of the data I am handling there.

Respondents in total: 14

10 9) Was the duration of summer school good or would you like to see it changed?

1. Make it longer next time, may be a minimum of 10 days.
2. Was good! Maybe starting on Monday afternoon would be good or not ending on a Monday but later in the week.
3. It was good
4. I would like it to be longer (10-14 days)
5. For this much content and with different level of people, I think needed more time so that everyone can learn properly. May be 2 week with the same content and more practice sessions.
6. Good or slightly longer, 7-10 days
7. I would like to see the summerschool be a bit longer actually. Just a bit too short to form meaningful connections. This though would require even more organisation, and maybe more content. That content could be at least a day of basic introduction to different subject (what is Fortran and how do you compile and run? What is climate and weather model? (which was there and was great) What IS AI and ML? etc.) Maybe this could also allow for a day of excursion to Helsinki for people coming from far away and wanting to see the city as well.
8. It was good, could have been a little longer
9. 10 days at least
10. I'd do 10 days instead of 7.
11. It should have been little more longer but overall its a good enough duration.
12. I would make it 5 days.
13. I think the duration was good.
14. It should be longer if possible, especially if the amount of topics covered is preferred to stay the same. For less topics and deeper diving into them, the duration might be enough.
15. It would probably help to have a few extra days (maybe 1-3) to have more time to grasp and apply all the concepts taught during the classes

Respondents in total: 15

11 10) Please give any other general comments or feedback about this event or any other issues arising from it.

1. May be some sight-seeing activities or trips could be combined, since this place so far away from the city, most of us didn't have any time for visiting it.
2. Don't forget the board games next time :D
3. Othee than the above mentioned ones, it was really Amazing experience and I learned very new things and hope to build more on it.
4. Thanks a lot! It was great!
5. Please don't put lecture on Sunday.
6. Getting valuable ideas and skills to eventually branch out from this course was very good to me.
7. The location was great, and it was nice that we got a lot of short breaks in between the lectures. Also, it was easy to approach the instructors and ask for help, as everyone was very friendly and approachable. With some changes, this would be a really good event! As a first trial run, however, the overall impression was still good :)
8. Thank you! I learned stuff, gained material and do not feel totally clueless now when I will have to do related tasks, which will come.
9. Except the points mentioned on questions 7) and 9), the overall experience from the summer school was great and it gave me basics and some tools to further learn by myself.

Respondents in total: 9

12 11) Overall, how would you rate this event?

1:	0 / 16
0 %	
2:	0 / 16
0 %	
3:	0 / 16
0 %	
4:	0 / 16
0 %	
5:	1 / 16
6 %	
6:	0 / 16
0 %	
7:	4 / 16
25 %	
8:	6 / 16
38 %	
9:	4 / 16
25 %	
10:	1 / 16
6 %	

Respondents in total: 16

avg. 7.94

11) Overall, how would you rate this event?

13 12) I consent that my course feedback can be published in the ESIWACE3's, WarmWorld's and / or CSC's reporting and marketing material (web site and/or other material). I agree that the afore mentioned organisations may edit my testimonial and publish also partial versions of it, however, they cannot alter, change or give misleading impressions of my views.

Yes:
100 %

12 / 12

Respondents in total: 12

avg. 1

course feedback can be published in the ESIWACE3's, WarmWorld's and / or CSC's reporting and marketing material (web site and/or other material). I agree that the afore mentioned organisations may edit my testimonial and publish also partial versions of it, however, they cannot alter, change or give misleading impressions of my views.